

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG MEDIUM ENTERPRISES EMPLOYEES

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Human Resource Management Practices and Job Satisfaction among Medium Enterprises Employees

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Abstract

This paper intends to investigate the relationship of human resource management practices (human resource recruitment, marketing management, financial management, and sales management) and job satisfaction among medium enterprise employees in service provider. The researchers used descriptive statistics to treat the problems, and Pearson r correlation to investigate the relationship of two variables. Results showed profile of the respondents had positive influence on job satisfaction among employees. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 level of significant. Further, human resource management practices in terms of human resource recruitment, marketing management, financial management, and sales management were oftentimes manifested that service providers are knowledgeable in different management skills in enterprises. The training, good relationship with superiors, co-employees, and skillful managers had substantial relationship on job satisfaction of the medium enterprise employees, considering the benefits as well as the effective good communication between subordinates and supervisor. In conclusion, this study contributes to the growing importance of skillful service provider. Additionally, the researcher found out that employees in Sultan Kudarat who are assigned in medium enterprises are highly satisfied on their job, thus implying that managers of the deferent sections of the business were knowledgeable in management skills such as in the recruitment of human resource, marketing management, financial, and sales management. Further, it can be concluded that findings of this study may serve as guiding principles for those who want to put up medium enterprises.

Keywords: *management, satisfaction, enterprises, employees*

Introduction

People are the most valuable resource, according to the mission statement found in practically all firms. Any business needs the appropriate people in the right places at the right times in order to accomplish its objectives, endure, and prosper (Oladipo, 2011). Like other commercial organizations, banking institutions rely heavily on the caliber and skill of its workforce. Consequently, companies need to focus more on their human resources since implementing HR procedures helps to maximize workers' competencies within the company (Saleem and Khurshid, 2014). When compared to competitors, human resource management techniques can produce businesses that are smart, adaptable, and competent. These companies follow procedures and policies for finding, hiring, and developing qualified workers. In response, these workers will put all of their energy into collaborating within the organization's resource pool (Nancy, 2013).

Additionally, the success, survival and competing power of the organizations are tied to the commitment of their members. For the members to be committed to their organization, they be satisfied with their job, that is to say employees' job satisfaction is supposed to be a crucial prerequisite for their commitment to their organization. Human resource management practices have a role to play in building a viable mutual relationship between firms and their employees concerning shared trust and duties. This relationship follows the "social exchange theory," in which employees offer their services to the organizations in exchange of perks and other benefits that they receive from the organizations (Mehwish et al., 2019).

Therefore, it is assumed that the reduction of the cost of employee turnover, absenteeism, low productivity can occur when employees are satisfied as well as well committed to their organization (Mohammad, et al. 2012). Personnel's achievements and their working capability are perquisites of their sense of job satisfaction (Paşaoğlu and Tonus, 2014). Thereby, for any organization (any bank, here) to attract new competent employees and maintain those existing talented ones, consistent human resource management practices, employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment should be considered and be among its priorities (Khera, 2010; Mizan et al., 2013).

"In the private, public, and civil society domains, customer service remains highly problematic. This is something that will undoubtedly preoccupy us in the days, months, and years to come. We can no longer accept a culture of mediocrity, either from Rwandan government institutions and business that provide services, or from Rwandan customers who silently accept subpar "customer care," if I may use that term" (Ibidem).

There are three medium Pobs and one city in Sultan Kudarat Province. consisting of medium-sized businesses. The community uses human resource management techniques, which are made up of many tribe and cultural customs with varying degrees of pleasure.

The purpose of this study is to look into the job satisfaction and HRM practices of employees in Sultan Kudarat's medium-sized businesses. Nevertheless, there is still unfilled research that needs to be done by researchers because it was not done in the previous study.

Research Questions

This study aims to answer the following questions;

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. marital status;
 - 1.4. educational attainment?
2. To what extent is the practices in managing human resources of the medium enterprises in terms of;
 - 2.1. human resources;
 - 2.2. marketing management;
 - 2.3. financial management
 - 2.4. sales management?
3. To what extent is the practices in managing human resources of the medium enterprise employees in Sultan Kudarat?
4. Is there a significant relationship between practices in managing human resources and job satisfaction of medium enterprise employees?
5. What HRM practices have you used to sustain your business?
6. What recruitment and selection strategies have you used to attract potential employees?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used mixed-method of research to explore the data both quantitative and qualitative data, so that information were more reliable and valid result of the study.

A phenomenological design is used to study a unique situation to explore human experiences over an extended period relating to specific events and what meaning the participants give to such experiences (Corby et al., 2015). A researcher using phenomenological design requires a fundamental belief in participants' interpretation of their experiences (Corby et al., 2015).

Participants

The respondents of the quantitative data was sale man assigned in three medium enterprise, who were working not less than 5 years in the business. The participants of the qualitative data was the store manager who were assigned in three business enterprise. They were 50 respondents to answer the constructed questionnaires in quantitative data and three participants to answer the focal group discussion related to qualitative data.

Instrument

Data collection instruments are tools that facilitate the collection of data from participants and secondary sources. According to McCusker and Gunaydin (2015), data collection instruments are critical in the qualitative research process, which serve as the fundamental tools to collect data from the participants. In this study, I served as the primary data collection instrument to interview and collect data from the participants (Yin, 2014).

For the Quantitative data, constructed questionnaires were distributed directly to the respondents, and after 45 to 60 minutes, the survey questionnaires were collected and ready for the tabulation and analysis of the data.

Procedure

The collection of data both quantitative and qualitative was sending letter to the respondents and business owner. After the approval of conducting study. The researcher administered the ready made constructed questionnaire by means of focal group discussion for qualitative questions, and distributed survey questionnaires for the quantitative data gathering for 45 to 60 minutes per respondents.

Data Analysis

This study employed central tendency mean and pearson correlation to interpret and described the quantitative data from the 50 respondents.

Yin (2014) posited the qualitative research method is appropriate for data analysis because researchers want to analyze real-world experiences of people. Various methods for analyzing data are available. Triangulation is the process of using multiple sources of data to bring about confidence in the findings of a study.

According to Fusch et al. (2018), triangulation in analyzing data minimizes bias, enhances data saturation, and adds depth to the data collected. Triangulation includes four different forms: (a) theoretical, (b) data, (c) investigative, and (d) methodological triangulation (Yin, 2014).

Ethical Considerations

The ethical researcher has the responsibility to ensure that participants do not face potential ethical issues that would harm the participants and potential consumers of the findings of the study. According to Petrova, Dewing, and Camilleri (2016), informed consent is an essential concept of moral and lawful requirements that protect human subjects in a study. A researcher must ensure that the four ethical principles are followed, suggested by Yin (2014): (a) respect participant's rights, (b) research should be of social good, (c) doing no harm, and (d) justice. I informed participants about the purpose of the study and ensured they agreed to or understood the potential risk, if any, they were likely to face as participants in the study. Sometimes asking people to discuss uncomfortable issues may bring anxiety; therefore, obtaining participants' informed consent gives the participants confidentiality, trust, and the assurance they are protected from harm. Where necessary, to ensure understanding of the research process by participants in the study for illiteracy reasons, verbal explanations regarding the research is appropriate to facilitate the participants' understanding. Tindana et al. (2012) used a verbal explanation regarding research to enhance participants' understanding of the process.

The informed consent letter ensured that participants for the study volunteered to take part in the study without coercion or any compensation. Participants had the right to withdraw from the study at any given time by informing me through phone, WhatsApp, or email. WhatsApp is one of the fastest and easiest communication applications on smartphones. For confidentiality, the participant's identity was not available in the data analysis following Warren and Szostek's (2017) example to help illustrate a coding system that did not reference the participant's business, but through a numbering system.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
18-22	2	4
23-27	15	30
28-32	25	50
33-37	6	12
38-42	2	4
Total	50	100%

Table 1 presented the result of statistical treatment in terms of age profile, the highest frequency was age bracket (28-32) with a frequency of twenty five (25) or fifty percent (50%), then age bracket (23-27) with a frequency of fifteen (15) or thirty percent (30%). The lowest frequency were bracket (18-22) and (38-42) with a frequency of two(2) or four percent (4%) consecutively. It implies that most of the respondents at the middle age, and age is positively associated with job satisfaction. This findings supported by the result of study Sarker, S.J (2021) revealed that employee age is not significantly associated with overall job satisfaction level, but that tenure is. There is also significant relationship between tenure and facets of satisfaction, but the effect of tenure on satisfaction is significantly modified by age.

Table 2. *Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	20	40.
Female	30	60.
Total	50	100%

Table 2 shows the findings in terms of sex, and the highest number of population was female with a frequency of thirty (30) or sixty percent (60%), then male was out number from female respondents at about twenty (20) or forty percent (40%). It implies that most of the business or enterprises were female worker.

Table 3. *Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Educational Attainment*

<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
High School Graduate	19	38
College Graduate	30	60
Master's Degree	1	2
Total	50	100%

Table 3 shows that out of fifty (50) respondents, the highest educational attainment was college graduate with a frequency of thirty (30) or sixty percent (60%), then item high school graduate had frequency of nineteen (19) or thirty eight percent (38%). The lowest frequency was item master's degree with a frequency of 1 or two percent (2%), it mean this master's degree was a manager of the business. It implies that most of the fresh graduate engage in business store or enterprises while on the process of struggling license or eligibility.

Table 4 revealed the responses of the respondents in terms of management practices of medium enterprises in terms of human resource, that the highest item was number two stated that building a positive work environment with a mean of 4.00 interpreted "Always" then

item number three stated that fostering open and honest feedback with a mean value of 3.50 described “Always”, then item number 1 compensating employees based on performance with the mean of 3.37 described “Oftentimes”, and item number 4 providing security to employees with a mean of 3.35 described as “Oftentimes”.

Table 4. *The practices in managing human resources of medium enterprises in terms of Human Resource in Sultan Kudarat*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Compensating employees based on performance	3.37	Oftentimes
Building a positive work environment	4.00	Always
Fostering open and honest feedback	3.50	Always
Providing security to employees	3.35	Oftentimes
Empowering teams to manage themselves.	2.55	Oftentimes
Section Mean	3.35	Oftentimes

Legend: 4.00-3.50 Always, 3.49- 2.50 Oftentimes, 2.49-1.50 Sometimes, 1.49-1.00 Never

Then the lowest mean value was item number 5 empowering teams to manage themselves with a mean value of 2.55 described “Oftentimes”. Then section mean was 3.35 described “Oftentimes”. Similar to this study was investigated by Cherif, F. (2020) stated that the role of human resource management and employee job satisfaction in predicting organizational commitment has positively correlated with job satisfaction. On the other hand, employee job satisfaction was found to be positively correlated with organizational commitment.

Table 5. *Shows the Practices in Managing Human Resources in terms of Marketing in Medium Enterprises in Sultan Kudarat*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
Identifying target audiences	2.40	Sometimes
The manager set attainable goals	2.55	Oftentimes
Determine your brand positioning	3.47	Oftentimes
Tailor your products and services to the customer, not the other way around.	3.00	Oftentimes
Conduct internal & external research	3.15	Oftentimes
Section Mean	2.92	Oftentimes

Legend: 4.00-3.50 Always, 3.49- 2.50 Oftentimes, 2.49-1.50 Sometimes, 1.49-1.00 Never

Table 5 shows the result of study in marketing management practices that medium enterprises employees shows a positive behavior, because in item number 3 determine brand positioning had a mean value of 3.47 described “Oftentimes” it means the behavior was manifested. The item number 5 stated that marketing management “Oftentimes” conduct internal and external research with a mean value of 3.15, then item number 4 with a mean of 3.00 described “Oftentimes” stated that marketing management tailor products and services to the customer, not the other way around. The lowest mean item number 1 with a value of 2.40 described “Sometimes” the management identifying target audiences. The section mean was 2.92 described “Oftentimes”. It implies that marketing management in-charge is knowledgeable in handling the skills of marketing. Similar study according to Omar. A et al (2017) revealed that human resource management in terms of marketing specifically had positive effect on the job satisfaction. Further, contributed to the maximum interest of the employee at their task assigned by the manager.

Table 6. *The Practices in Managing Human Resources in Terms of Financial in Medium Enterprises in Sultan Kudarat*

<i>Statement</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
A realistic budget must be created and followed in order to preserve good finances.	2.35	Sometimes
Inventory management helps companies identify which and how much stock to order at what time.	2.40	Sometimes
Practices for developing and implementing financial risk management.	2.55	Oftentimes
Effective cash flow management involves monitoring cash inflows and outflows.	3.20	Oftentimes
Ensuring accurate financial reporting	3.40	Oftentimes
Section Mean	2.78	Oftentimes

Legend: 4.00-3.50 Always, 3.49- 2.50 Oftentimes, 2.49-1.50 Sometimes, 1.49-1.00 Never

Table 6 revealed by the fifty respondents that the highest mean value in financial management was item number 5 that manager ensuring accurate financial reporting of the business with a value mean of 3.40 described “Oftentimes”, then followed by the item number 4 stated that effective cash flow management involves monitoring cash inflows and outflows rated a mean of 3.20 described “Oftentimes”. In five item, the lowest mean was item number 1 with the value of 2.35, and item number 2 with the value mean of 2.40 consecutively described “Sometimes” that financial manager was realistic in budgeting that they must be created and followed in order to preserve good finance, and additionally manager was conducting inventory management to helps companies identify which and how much stock

to order at what time. The section mean was 2.78 described “Oftentimes”. This implies that financial manager assigned in the task is familiar with the financial management. Further, this two domains explore in research were job satisfaction and financial marketing so that company improve capital efficiency, maintain cash flow, pay regularly the debts and oversee finances.

Table 7. Shows the Practices in Managing Human Resources in Terms of Sales in Medium Enterprises in Sultan Kudarat

Statement	Mean	Verbal Description
Empower your salespeople	3.55	Always
Customer relationship management	2.40	Sometimes
Create a motivating culture	3.40	Oftentimes
Creating sales plans and workflows	3.35	Oftentimes
Incentivize your sales team	3.57	Always
Section Mean	3.25	Oftentimes

Legend: 4.00-3.50 Always, 3.49- 2.50 Oftentimes, 2.49-1.50 Sometimes, 1.49-1.00 Never

Table 7 revealed the highest mean value in the sales management, the highest value mean was item number 5 incentives sales team described “Always” with the mean of 3.57, and followed by the item number 1 empower salespeople with a mean of 3.55 described “Always”, and item number 3 create a motivating culture with a mean of 3.40 described “Oftentimes”. The lowest mean was item number 2 customer relationship management with a mean value of 2.40 described “Sometimes”. The section mean was 3.25 described “Oftentimes”. It implies that sales manager with positive behavior in handling sale lady or sales men. Further, satisfied employees are willing to go the extra mile to contribute to the company’s success, resulting in higher overall performance.

Table 8. Shows the Extent of Job Satisfaction of Medium Enterprises in Sultan Kudarat

Statement	Mean	Verbal Description
Have more control over how you get your work done.	2.40	Satisfied
Value work/life boundaries and you stick to them	2.35	Satisfied
Have the freedom to experiment and make mistakes.	3.25	Highly Satisfied
Have work friends or people you can lean on.	3.57	Very Highly Satisfied
Get good feedback on how you are doing.	3.00	Highly Satisfied
With appreciation for the work	3.55	Very Highly Satisfied
With good relationships with superiors	3.58	Very Highly Satisfied
With company’s financial stability	3.25	Highly Satisfied
Fair and competitive salary	2.55	Highly Satisfied
Good work with life balance	3.00	Highly Satisfied
Section Mean	3.05	Highly Satisfied

Legend: 4.00-3.50 Always, 3.49- 2.50 Oftentimes, 2.49-1.50 Sometimes, 1.49-1.00 Never

Table 8 shows the responses of the respondents in terms of job satisfaction among medium enterprise employees. They were ten indicators to evaluate the job satisfaction, and among the ten manifestation, the highest mean was item number 7 with a mean of 3.58, item 6 with a mean of 3.55, and item number 4 with a mean value of 3.57 consecutively described “Very Highly Satisfied”. These manifestations are employees feel that their work appreciated, and feel good relationship with superiors, and have work friends or people can lean on in the company. However, the lowest mean was item number 1 with the value of 2.40 described “Satisfied” stated that have more control over how you get your work done, and item number 2 with a mean value of 2.35 described “Satisfied” on value work and stick to them. The section mean was 3.05 described “Highly Satisfied”. It implies that the manager of the medium enterprises in the deferent department manifested a good behavior and with skills in management that contributed to the job satisfaction of the employees. This findings supported by the output of the study by Mondejar, H.(2022) that human resource management practices associated with job satisfaction, and by that researcher found out that, their was a positive correlated between management practices and job satisfaction.

Table 9. Matrix of Correlation Analysis Between Practices in Managing Human Resources and Job Satisfaction of the Medium Enterprise Employees

Variables	Sig.	r-value	Interpretation
Human Resources	0.063 Sig.	.619	Substantial Relationship
Marketing Management	0.081 Sig.	.660	Substantial Relationship
Financial Management	0.072 Sig.	.681	Substantial Relationship
Sales Management	0.088 Sig.	.628	Substantial Relationship

Significant at 0.05 Level

Table 9 result of matrix of analysis revealed that human resource management practices such as the human resource with computer r-value of .619, marketing management r-value of .660, financial management r-value of .681, and sales management r-value of .628 consecutively significant at 0.05 level and interpreted a positively correlated with the job satisfaction described a substantial relationship. Therefor, the null hypothesis was rejected. It implies that employees satisfied when the manager of the company knowledgeable on the different human resource management practices. His findings, similar to the study of Omar. A et al (2017) that human resource management practices associated with the employees job satisfaction or employees performance.

Presentation of the Qualitative Findings

With the application of Yin's (2017) five-step manual analysis, my study revealed six key themes related to the success of ME's beyond 5 years. Table 10 contains the six key themes that resulted from my analysis.

Table 10. *Summary of Key Themes*

<i>Key Themes</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Human resource as Critical Assets	15
Training and Development	13
Compensation and Benefits	12
Recruitment and Selection	5
Involvement in Decision Making	3
The God Factor	2

The central research question for this study was, What HRM strategies do ME leaders use to sustain their business beyond 5 years? Using individual interviews, a focus group, and a review of business records, key themes were identified. Between my findings and the conceptual framework of Blau's (1964) social exchange theory, I established alignment. Methodological triangulation was achieved through the use of common themes discovered through the interview process, focus group discussion, review of the administrative manual, literature reviews. Denzin and Giardina (2016) posited that data saturation is necessary for comprehensive qualitative case study research.

Theme 1: Human Resource as Critical Asset

An organization cannot function sustainably without the appropriate HR base. Human capital, as the most critical asset of the organization, was the first theme to emerge from the individual face-to-face interviews. Supported by previous research, Nolan and Garavan (2016) noted that human resource staffing in MEs is essential for business sustainability. All participants (PS1, PS2, PSG3, and PSG4) in their first responses noted that without considering the employees as the most critical asset of the organization, they would not have survived to this date. PS2 emphasized, "We have always maintained that the employee is the most important asset." PS1 stated that "We recognize the employees as critical assets to the organization." PSG3 and PSG4 also admitted that the employees are essential for the business. "Though the business is mine, I make them feel belonging to the business," emphasized PSG4.

Responses of focus group participants' (FG1, FG2, FG3, FG4, FG5, and FG6) validated the statement that HR is the most critical asset of the company. Four out of six focus group participants felt that the way the leaders related to them indicated they are essential, and that made them give their best to their jobs. The conceptual framework of this study, the social exchange theory (Blau, 1964), aligns with the focus group participants' statements in the sense that building a conducive work environment thrives on the social exchange between the employer and the employee. The exchange of leadership respect and employee work devotion demonstrates Blau's (1964) social exchange theory through a transaction that is mutually beneficial for both parties.

Two focus group participants also mentioned their involvement in planning and making certain critical decisions, even in the absence of their bosses, made them feel great. The responses provided by the participants in this qualitative multiple case study were also concurrent with the findings in the literature.

As revealed by Chakraborty and Biswas (2019), the employee stands critical as an integral part of the organization because they are the precious assets of the organization.

Based on the findings above, leaders of MEs must maintain their employees, just like any other asset of the organization, because the role of the employee has become more pronounced and significant in the sustainability of an organization in creating a healthy work environment for competitive business advantage. Table 11 represents some comments from the four ME leaders who participated in the face-to-face interviews, specifically on the question regarding what HRM practices they have used to sustain their businesses.

Table 11. *Theme 1: Human Resource as Critical Asset*

<i>Participant</i>	<i>Participant comments</i>
PS1	We recognize the employees as critical assets to the organization
PS2	We have always maintained that the employee is the most important asset
PSG3	They are very important for our business though the business is mine.
PSG4	This makes the workers happy, and they feel like they have another family who cares for them

Table 12. *Theme 2: Training and Development*

<i>Participant</i>	<i>Participant comments</i>
PS1	We prepare employees to take up potential positions to be able to adapt to new things in the industry
PS2	Another strategy is to bring an expert from outside to come and give specific or specified training for a department
PSG3	Training on the job to meet customers changing dynamics
PSG4	I monitored and realized that was the cause of some of the bread not being well baked, so I was there myself to give on the job training on timing

Theme 2: Training and Development

Training and development emerged as the second theme. All participants spoke about the need to invest in training and the need for continuously updating the SKAs of the employees to be relevant to the dynamics of the work environment and be motivated to support business competition. Cosmides (1987) posited that the successful engagement of individuals for mutual benefit involves social exchange cooperation by which humans can solve problems through training and other opportunities for advancement within the organization. Organizations that do not invest in their employees or provide a conducive atmosphere to train and develop their employees risk being irrelevant and unsustainable (Giblin & Galli, 2017).

PS1 noted that once the employee is hired, there is the need for orientation to prepare the employee to fit into the culture and tradition of the organization, which PS1 said forms part of the initial training on the job. Findings in the literature are consistent with this theme; Ahmad (2015) stated that training should start from orientation and continue through all levels of the organization. PS1 commented that orientation is essential to let the employee understand the culture and tradition of the organization.

PSG3 said, “We take them through what they are supposed to be doing and doing it the best way.” Gauche, de Beer, and Brink (2017) stated the importance of giving opportunities to employees to gain practical experience in the implementation of new jobs so they can benefit from job enrichment in the job processes and commit to the organization’s sustainable effort. PS2 mentioned, “We ensure that the staff builds the capacity on the job and outside the premises of the organization.” In the same manner, training and development can be accomplished internally or externally, as indicated by PS1. PS2 commented, “internal training is where our supervisors are trained, and they become the trainer of trainees for quality sustainability of our standards in addition to external training where employees are sent out on short or long-term courses.” Chakraborty and Biswas (2019) posited that training and development is a strategy for talent management to augment the efficient performance of the organization to gain competitive advantage substantially and sustainably. PSG4 commented, “the training, especially on the job training for customer care, is a continuous thing to ensure business continuity and sustainability.”

All four participants’ comments validated Khan et al.’s (2016) work by stating that training and development are activities planned to assist the learning related to job knowledge, skills, and employees. All six focus group participants validated the positions of all the four individual participants’ views on training and development. FG1 said, “For that one, I will say a lot, I have been able to advance myself through training to develop myself over the years, it is not every organization that you get the opportunity to go back to school.” FG2 said, “I have also learned a lot, especially teamwork and encouragement.” FG3 also said, “I have also improved in my education during the period I have been here, I used to be a shy person, but now I am not, I can stand in public and talk.” The other three FG participants generally agreed that without training, two things could likely happen, (a) no new skills, no job satisfaction, and (b) no self-development to help you when you leave the organization. Comments by PS1, PS2, PSG3, and PSG4 were consistent with the literature review, which revealed that training is the acquisition of skills and knowledge to perform a present task and contribute to the organization's success in the employee’s current state. At the same time, development is the acquisition of skills and knowledge that may be used in the present or in the future geared towards the preparation of the individual to enrich the organization.

HR Challenge in Training and Development

Although participants were unanimous in the view that training and development are essential investments, two of the participants noted that training and development come with an organizational cost and, therefore, an HRM challenge. When an employee receives training, and that employee decides to quit without any prior notice, it creates an HR challenge. PSG4 said, “One of the challenges is the unannounced departure of some workers, there are some, once you update their skills and they know how to do something small then they just run away.” PSG3 lamented an HRM challenge related to training and development as follows: “Except that when you give training to a worker over a period, and the person decides to leave the work without any prior notice, is a challenge and additional cost that we have experience as an organization.” FG1 supported the lamentations of the two leaders' training and development challenges. FG1 noted, “The other challenge which has not happened here is when you give people training, then they just go for further study and will not come and contribute their new knowledge to the employers. This has happened in some organizations.” The above challenge is validated by Mayanja and Perks (2017), who stated that some leaders of MEs do not take advantage of training and development because of the financial investment involved. Also, trained employees may leave the organization with new knowledge and sign on with another competitor.

However, this HRM challenge may be addressed through proper motivation once the employee is successfully trained. ME leaders should not see the training of the employee as a privilege. Viewing training as a privilege may lead to the employee leaving for another competitor with the new skills and knowledge acquired. But Ahmad (2015) indicated that appropriate orientation and induction of the employee into the core values, culture, tradition of the organization, and proper compensation, benefits, and welfare systems would help minimize such challenges. Ahmad’s statement validated PS2’s comments of, Well, so then you become a family member and, by extension, a team player to bring to bear the new set of skills, knowledge, and abilities the employee has acquired onto their jobs to help move the business on a competitive advantage path. Also, there is appropriate rewards and adjustment to motivate the person to stay. Otherwise, you may lose the loyalty of the person to another competitor organization. PS2 went on to say that, “It is this kind of experienced that has retained more than 20 staff to be with the organization since the inception (21yrs) in business.” Table 13 represents some comments from the four ME leaders who participated in the face-toface interview regarding Theme 13, training and development

as a strategy for ME sustainability.

Table 13. *Theme 3: Compensation and Benefits*

<i>Participant</i>	<i>Participant comments</i>
PS1	I think that staff welfare is one of the strategies we have constantly maintained over the years in addition to the salaries and wages we pay
PS2	We have the policy to assist staff four years in the job to buy landed property at their place of choice. Also, there is the 13th-month salary Also, once you are good at what you are doing, there is recognition and rewards which are used to retain some workers
PSG3	
PSG4	We also pay their social security, which is very important for them, and when profit is made, we share the profit by way of salary increase

Theme 3: Compensation and Benefits

Compensation and benefits emerged as the third theme through all the four interview participants and focus group discussions. The conceptual framework, the social exchange theory which underlines this study, stated social exchange is the voluntary actions of individuals motivated by the expected returns for their engagement (Blau,

1964). In any type of engagement, there is an expected return both ways. Supported by Reddy (2017), compensation based on the social exchange theory represents an exchange between the employee and the employer. The actions of the employee to positively impact the performance of the organization is based on the motivation of the social exchange agreement. The third theme of compensation and benefits as an integral part of motivating workers appears in the interview responses below. PS1, PS2, PS3, and PS4 all said that besides the monthly salaries or weekly wages, other benefits for motivation are a crucial factor in attracting, retaining, and maintaining employees for building a sustainable organization. Benstead (2019) posited that one way to be sure that your business will succeed is to take care of your employees. Fair treatment, strong employee management, in addition to providing opportunities, constitute a vital strategy to help you achieve your business objectives. PS2 said, "in addition to salaries and wages that we pay, we also have the policy to assist staff four years on the job to buy landed property at their place of choice, we also give them 13th-month benefit which some other enterprises do not do." Both PS1 and PS2 stated that some of the HRM strategies they have adopted under Theme 3 have helped them retain some of the staff since the inception of their organization spanning over 18 years. PSG4 said, "Alhaji has been with us since his employment about 18yrs ago." Two focus group participants collaborated on what PS1, PS2, and PSG4 said. One of the focus group participants said he could not stay longer in an organization where there are no "side issues," meaning he cannot stay longer with an employer where there are no additional benefits or motivation.

The importance of compensation and benefits in enterprise sustainability was validated by Iswan (2017), who posited that compensation and benefits management plan requires arrangements for employees to be motivated for performance, improve prosperity, spur and improve productivity for competitive advantage for firm sustainability. All focus group participants validated the consistent management dynamic of compensation and benefits as a necessary exchange for firm continuity. Table 4 represents comments from the four ME leaders who participated in the face-to-face interview regarding salary and benefits as an essential strategy for ME sustainability.

Theme 4: Recruitment and Selection

Table 5. *Theme 4: Recruitment and Selection*

<i>Participant</i>	<i>Participant comments</i>
PS1	We observe the potential employee's attitude to get the selected employee's fit into the culture and tradition of the company
PS2	Our recruitment and selection strategy is done case by case, for the higher level we pray about it, we ask for a recommendation from people, both externally and internally
PSG3	Our strategy for recruitment and selection is radio advertisement and sometimes walk in and recommendations
PSG4	Normally you see them they will just walk in that they want work to do, we also sometimes do radio announcements. Also, I speak with people for referrals When we meet them, we look at their ability, and we select them for the different sections where we need workers. Well during the interview some will fail, and they will come crying

Recruitment and selection, as HRM practices, are a well-documented strategy used by organizations. Attracting, recruiting, and maintaining the right people with the appropriate SKA's may increase the performance and, subsequently, the sustainability of the organization (Florea & Mihai, 2014). The people make up the organization, and the human factor is the key to success in an organization.

All participants were unanimous about the use of radio advertisements, referrals, and recommendations for recruitment and selection of potential candidates. Schlachter and Pieper (2019) posited that referrals, recommendations, and walk-in recruitment could leverage cost savings to the organization. None of the participants used recruitment agencies to fill vacancies as they become available. PS2

inferred that in their organization, the recruitment and selection of new employees are conducted on a case by case basis. For higher-level positions, it is mainly by recommendation and referral, both internal and external. A radio advertisement is used for lower-level staff recruitment.

PS1 preferred filling positions in the organization through internship and national service personnel by observation of the attitude of the intern or service personnel for the right job, after which if there is no fit for the position, then external recruitment is considered. PS1 said, "The right people for the right positions. Our strategy is to observe the intern's attitude before consideration to retain." PSG3 and PS4 were unanimous that they have a lot of walk-ins, including disabled people they consider. "As we speak, I am about to interview a deaf and dumb applicant," PSG4 commented.

Some FG participants stated they came into their employment through referrals, and recommendations after which a simple interview was held to test the abilities for the positions. FG participant's comments were consistent with the recruitment and selection processes outlined by the leaders. FG participant1 said, "I was retained after my national service." The cost of recruitment and selection can be expensive for MEs. Withiel, Dpsych, Man, Physio, & Juj (2020) posited that these costs encompass direct costs associated with recruitment, as well as indirect costs related to lost productivity and training. Because of the limited nature of resources, recommendations, referrals, and retaining of interns and national service personnel minimizes the cost involved in the recruitment and selection in MEs (Withiel et al., 2020).

Participant's experiences were in alignment with the extension of the social exchange framework by Tremblay and Simard (2005). They stated that successful organizations had established favorable relationships leading to external referrals and recommendations for people with the right skills to be recruited to fit in the right positions or retain talented employees in their jobs or new positions. Table 5 documents comments from ME leaders on their experiences with the fourth theme, recruitment, and selection.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study:

The study aim to investigate the implication of human resource recruitment management practices on the job satisfaction of employees in medium enterprises in Sultan Kudarat, and the researcher found out that employees in Sultan Kudarat who assigned in medium enterprises are highly satisfied on their job and it implies that manager of the deferent sections of the business were knowledgeable in management skills such as in the recruitment of human resource, marketing management, financial, and sales management. Further, concluded that findings of this study may served as guiding principles for those who want to put up medium enterprises.

The researcher may recommend to adopt the guidelines and policies of the medium enterprise in Sultan Kudarat.

The researcher may address some variables doesn't part of the study to reconduct.

The researcher may recommend the medium enterprise to initiate training on sales management and marketing management to ensure the high percentage of skillful manager in dealing with sales lady and marketing personnel.

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